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From Findings to Demands: The Legal Significance of the Genocide Report by the UN Commission of Inquiry

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By **Diego Sanchez Borjas**

Introduction

On September, 16th 2025, the Independent International Commission of Inquiry on the Occupied Palestinian Territory (the “COI”) released its detailed findings (the “Findings document”) on the conduct of Israel in the Gaza Strip under the Genocide Convention (the “Convention”). The Findings document was summarised in the report submitted by the COI to the UN General Assembly (the “GA”) and the UN Human Rights Council (the “Council”) on September, 14th 2025 (the “COI Report”; §2).

Based on evidence collected, the Findings document concluded *inter alia* that “...the State of Israel bears responsibility for the failure to prevent genocide, the commission of genocide and the failure to punish genocide against the Palestinians in the Gaza Strip” (§255). Thereby setting out, under the mandate of the Council, a legal characterisation of the atrocities carried out in the context of the Israeli military occupation and siege of the Gaza Strip since October 2023.

The present post addresses the question of the legal value and effects of the COI’s Report vis-à-vis the United Nations and Member States.

The COI’s mandate and relation to the Genocide Convention

Under A/HRC/RES/S-30/1, the COI was established to conduct investigations of alleged violations and abuses of international humanitarian law and international human rights law (op. clause 1). Notably, the COI was empowered specifically to “[e]stablish the facts and circumstances that may amount to such violations and abuses and of crimes perpetrated” (op. clause 2, para. (a)).

Nonetheless, the investigation of alleged violations specifically under the Convention was not included within the COI’s mandate. Notwithstanding that, the COI’s Terms of Reference (the “ToR”) indicate that it will “consider other obligations under international law as applicable and where relevant” (p. 4). It

is, thus, relevant that the COI established in the Findings document that the facts upon which it carried out its legal analysis relied on previous reports submitted to the Council (§2; see [A/HRC/56/26](#); [A/79/232](#); [A/HRC/59/26](#)). In doing so, the COI appears to establish a connection between the violations of international humanitarian law and international human rights law found in those reports, and the underlying acts of genocide per Article II of the Convention (§§3-4). Here concerning the abuses and violations carried out by Israeli military officials or its agents in the Gaza Strip that constitute war crimes and crimes against humanity (§2 of the Findings document).

Thereby, the Findings document underscore how the facts as established in previous reports (§16), which fall into the COI's specific mandate, have enabled the COI to inquire into the legal qualification of the acts attributed to the State of Israel and the legal consequences arising thereof.

What is the legal value of the Report under international law?

The present section intends to examine whether any legal value can be ascribed to the COI Report under international law. For the purposes of this section, any reference to a COI must be understood to a Commission of Inquiry in broader sense and not limited to the Commission of Inquiry related to the situation in Gaza.

As noted by scholarly commentary ([here](#)) and the UN Office of the High Commissioner of Human Rights ([here](#)), a COI is not a criminal tribunal nor a judicial body or organ under international law. Although a COI appears to have imported the standard of proof used by international criminal tribunals or jurisdictions, there is no discussion about their findings lacking the same legal value as a judgement based upon facts and the findings of international and/or criminal responsibility. Nevertheless, reports from others COI have been cited and invoked before international tribunals, a fact which clarifies their persuasive value, particularly concerning their relevance in establishing context and facts to later sustain (successful) prosecutions ([here](#), [here](#)).

In international practice, some international courts have engaged directly with COI reports when determining and establishing the facts upon which the legal assessment had to be applied. For instance, the ICJ in the 2007

Application of Genocide Convention judgement (§27) laid down the criteria to weigh the value of reports (including, *inter alia*, COI reports): (i) the origin or source (i.e. neutrality), (ii) the methodology (i.e. whether the report used a court-like process), and (iii) the quality or character of the information contained. To exemplify the relevance of the criteria above, the recent Order on Provisional Measures on *South Africa v Israel* underscores how the ICJ weighed on favourably the reports of UN officials' statements (§47), UN agencies reports and statements (§§46,48-49) and the Special Procedures of the Council statement (§53) on the situation in Gaza to conclude on the plausibility of the commission of genocidal acts under Article III of the Convention. Further, in the field of international criminal law, as noted by scholarly commentary, COI reports have contributed, albeit indirectly, to the work of ad-hoc international criminal tribunals in the process of collecting evidence to establish individual criminal responsibility.

In that regard, the legal value of the COI Report under international law may fall into Article 38(1)(d) of the ICJ Statute. Either to determine the context, facts or to establish responsibility in the context of international courts' proceedings, the COI Report aligns with the abovementioned provision insofar as it informs or elucidates the meaning and application of existing rules of international law. To establish this legal characterisation, the work of the International Law Commission (the "ILC") will be examined. During its analysis of the elements to identify subsidiary means for the determination of the rules of international law, the ILC (2025, §128) has acknowledged the work of State-created expert bodies. Any body would fall into this category if four elements are met: (i) an expert body created by States, (ii) consisting of experts nominated and elected by States, (iii) they serve in their personal capacity, and (iv) the body is created by, *inter alia*, a resolution.

The COI is an expert body created by the Council, a subsidiary organ of the GA where 47 Member States are elected as Members (A/RES/60/251, op. clause 1). The COI is composed of renowned experts in the field of international law, human rights law and international human rights law (here). They were nominated by the Council President to act in their personal capacity within the terms of the mandate under Council Resolution S-30/1 (op. clause 1). Based upon the ICJ's criteria laid down above, it can also be contended that the COI report, to the extent that it is elaborated by a Council-mandated body, is neutral and possesses a highly relevant value given the use of a court-like

process to collect the evidence used to establish its findings. As noted by some scholars, the COI when discharging their fact-finding mission reaches its findings on the basis of evidence available to them and weigh the value of the evidence collected against corroboration relying on court-like thresholds (i.e. the COI used a “reasonable grounds” threshold, p. 5 ToR; see for further study here, here).

Accordingly, the COI Report would fall into the State-created expert body category, as defined by the ILC, to establish the legal value of its work under Article 38(1)(d) of the ICJ Statute as a subsidiary means to determine existing rules of international law.

Is the Report binding on the United Nations (and its Members)?

The present section will examine what are the legal effects of the Report vis-à-vis States in addition to discussing whether it can be enforced through the action of the GA (as the COI acts within the Council's scope).

The Convention does not condition (or limit) States Parties' actions to the finding of an international court or tribunal that genocide was committed. This proposition can be inferred from the legal finding that State responsibility under the Convention can be incurred even without any previous finding of individual criminal responsibility (*Application of Genocide Convention*, §182). An interpretation that is supported in the Findings document (§246) that elucidate that a State Party to the Convention should assess if a serious risk of genocide exists to comply with its obligation to prevent the commission of genocide.

While the COI Report is considered as a subsidiary means for determining rules according to Article 38 ICJ Statute, it can also serve as supplementary guidance for treaty interpretation under Article 32 VCLT (ILC, 2025, §420). To the extent that general rules of treaty interpretation are insufficient for a State Party (or courts) to establish whether the acts carried out by the State of Israel fall into the abstract wording of the Convention, the Findings as upheld by the COI Report provide authoritative guidance on whether the commission of such acts by Israel or its agents constitute prohibited acts under the Convention.

Further, the COI acts within the scope of the mandate as agreed upon by the Council. In that light, the Council is a subsidiary organ of the GA per Article 22 of the UN Charter. Hence, the GA acts through the Council to discharge its functions related to, *inter alia*, (i) the promotion of universal respect for human rights, and (ii) addressing situations of violations of human rights (A/RES/60/251, op. clauses 2, 3). These violations, as noted above, can also constitute breaches of *ius cogens* norms, namely as provided in the Convention.

Nonetheless, the Council resolution upholding the COI Report would not be sufficient to create a binding effect on the GA. Although the Council is discharging the functions of the GA, there is no express provision in its founding resolution that establishes the duty of the GA to adhere or be bound by the Council decisions or actions (cfr. *Effect of Awards of Compensation Made by the UNAT*, p. 61). Hence, the mere adoption of a Council decision upholding the COI Report is not sufficient to create a binding effect upon the GA. This is a practice confirmed, for instance, in the adoption of the Report of the UN Fact-Finding Mission on the Gaza Conflict in 2008 in which the Council, after adopting a resolution upholding the report, called for the GA to expressly endorse the report, which it ultimately did (for further study on this report see here).

To that end, for the GA to act on the COI Report, it would be necessary to adopt an independent resolution based upon the reference made by a Council resolution. This sequence enables the GA to adopt the conclusions and findings of the COI Report as their own to the extent that they have been endorsed by the Council, the subsidiary organ created to discharge the GA's functions in human rights matters (*Certain Expenses*, ICJ, pp. 15,18).

Consequently, the GA may decide to recommend, per Article 11(2) of the UN Charter, to the Security Council to act under Chapter VII to restore international peace and security, particularly due to the commission of grave crimes under international law (*Certain Expenses*, pp. 17-18). Should the Security Council fail to take action, the GA may reconvene an Emergency Special Session and consider the adoption of recommendations to seek the cessation of the State of Israel's actions included in the COI Report (see here, here, here).

Conclusion

Returning to the post's question: the COI Report may be characterised as subsidiary means for the determination of rules emanating from the GC per Article 38(1)(d) of the ICJ Statute. Specially, to assist in the States' cognition of the existence of a serious risk of genocide and, to the extent that acts of genocide were carried out by the State of Israel, what measures should it implement to observe that these acts are effectively investigated and punished. Further, as the GA is not bound by the Council's decision upholding the COI Report, it is necessary for the GA to act on a separate resolution to make recommendations based on said findings under the Convention.

Diego Sanchez Borjas ([ORCID](#)) is a PhD Candidate in Public International Law at Universitat Pompeu Fabra (Barcelona) and a lawyer

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